

Studies on Some Phosphotellurates and Phosphomolybdotellurates

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Ammonium phosphotellurate, $3(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O} \cdot 2\text{TeO}_3 \cdot 3\text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and its salts with barium, copper, and cuprammonium have been prepared and their properties studied. The compositions given have been confirmed by conductometric titration. Ammonium phosphotellurato-molybdate and its barium salt have also been prepared and their compositions arrived at on the basis of analytical results.

According to Weinland and Prause¹, telluric acid forms compounds with phosphates and arsenates. They obtained ammonium diphosphato-tellurate, $2(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O} \cdot \text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot \text{TeO}_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, by evaporating a solution of 2 moles of phosphoric acid, one mole of telluric acid, and 4 moles of ammonia. By changing the ratio of the three components, they also prepared another phosphotellurate of the composition $4(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O} \cdot 3\text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 2\text{TeO}_3 \cdot 11\text{H}_2\text{O}$. They also prepared a sodium phosphotellurate of the composition $2\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 2\text{TeO}_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Gibbs² obtained two ammonium phosphovanadomolybdates:

by boiling ammonium phosphomolybdate with ammonium vanadate solution. Later Blum³ confirmed Gibbs' view, showing the possibility of condensation of phosphorus pentoxide, vanadium pentoxide, and molybdic oxide and isolated $5(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O} \cdot \text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 11\text{V}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 11\text{MoO}_3 \cdot 50\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Telluric acid has also been condensed to form heteropoly salts with molybdic acid by several workers⁴⁻⁶. Recently ammonium tellurato-tetramolybdate has been prepared in this laboratory⁷.

The present investigation was therefore undertaken to study the condensation reactions of telluric acid with phosphoric and molybdic acids. This communication deals with the results of the preparation and analysis of a new ammonium phosphotellurate and its salts with barium, copper, and cuprammonium. The formation of barium and copper salts has been confirmed by conductometric titration. Ammonium phosphotellurato-molybdate and its barium salt have also been prepared.

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2. *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1883, **5**, 391.
3. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, **30**, 1858.
4. Miolati, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1910, **70**, 330.
5. Maloche and Woodstock, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 171.
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EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were of E. Merck or B. D. H. pure quality.

Ammonium Phosphotellurate.—Telluric acid (1*M*) and phosphoric acid (4*M*) were dissolved in water and sufficient quantity of liquor ammonia was added to the solution and the mixture was refluxed for 6 hr. The clear solution obtained was evaporated to a small volume, slightly acidified with acetic acid, and kept in a refrigerator for crystallisation. After four days, a white crystalline solid separated. It was recrystallised from water and dried in a vacuum desiccator over fused calcium chloride and then over solid KOH to remove excess of acetic acid. It is stable at the room temperature but decomposes on heating. [Found: $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O}$, 13.85; TeO_3 , 31.35; P_2O_5 , 37.82; H_2O , 16.90. Calc. for $3(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O} \cdot 2\text{TeO}_3 \cdot 3\text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$: $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O}$, 14.02; TeO_3 , 31.56; P_2O_5 , 38.26, H_2O , 16.17%].

Barium salt was prepared by adding aqueous solution of barium chloride to ammonium salt solution. It is a white powder, insoluble in water and ethanol. (Found: BaO , 37.01; TeO_3 , 27.42; P_2O_5 , 33.05, H_2O , 1.46. Calc. for $3\text{BaO} \cdot 2\text{TeO}_3 \cdot 3\text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$: BaO , 36.66; TeO_3 , 27.99; P_2O_5 , 33.93; H_2O , 1.43%].

Copper Salt.—When a dilute solution of copper sulphate was added to the ammonium salt solution, a bluish compound separated. [Found: CuO , 20.98; TeO_3 , 31.96; P_2O_5 , 39.64; H_2O , 6.70. Calc. for $3\text{CuO} \cdot 2\text{TeO}_3 \cdot 3\text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$: CuO , 21.94; TeO_3 , 32.29; P_2O_5 , 39.16; H_2O , 6.62%].

Cuprammonium Salt.—A freshly prepared solution of cuprammonium sulphate furnished a greenish precipitate when added to the ammonium phosphotellurate solution. [Found: Cu , 13.99; NH_3 , 15.01; TeO_3 , 26.21; P_2O_5 , 31.96; H_2O , 8.02. Calc. for $3 \left[\begin{array}{c} \text{NH}_3 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{Cu} \\ \diagup \\ \text{NH}_3 \end{array} \right] \cdot 0.2\text{TeO}_3 \cdot 3\text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Cu , 14.35; NH_3 , 15.37; TeO_3 , 26.46; P_2O_5 , 32.98; H_2O , 8.13%].

Ammonium Phosphotellurato-molybdate.—Telluric acid (4.6 g.), molybdic acid (30g.), and phosphoric acid (17.5 g.) were dissolved in liquor ammonia and the solution was refluxed for 10 hr. The clear solution was evaporated to a small volume and kept in a refrigerator for crystallisation. It is a white crystalline solid, stable at the room temperature but decomposes when heated. It is decomposed by strong acid or alkali solutions. [Found: $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O}$, 9.78; TeO_3 , 20.34; P_2O_5 , 3.41; MoO_3 , 62.06; H_2O , 4.18. Calc. for $8(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O} \cdot 5\text{TeO}_3 \cdot \text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 18\text{MoO}_3 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$: $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O}$, 9.89; TeO_3 , 20.86; P_2O_5 , 3.37; MoO_3 , 61.60; H_2O , 4.28%].

Barium phosphotellurato-molybdate was obtained as a white powder when a dilute solution of barium chloride was added to the solution of ammonium salt. [Found: BaO , 24.98; TeO_3 , 17.60; P_2O_5 , 2.75; MoO_3 , 51.38; H_2O , 2.16. Calc. for $8\text{BaO} \cdot 5\text{TeO}_3 \cdot \text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 18\text{MoO}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$: BaO , 24.79; TeO_3 , 17.75; P_2O_5 , 2.87; MoO_3 , 52.40; H_2O , 2.18%].

Estimations.—For the estimation of ammonia, the sample was treated with an excess of NaOH solution and the liberated ammonia distilled into a standard solution of HCl. The excess acid was back-titrated against a standard NaOH solution. Phosphorus was estimated as $\text{Mg}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$, tellurium as metallic tellurium, barium as BaSO_4 , copper as CuSO_4

iodometrically and molybdenum as molybdenum sulphide and igniting to MoO_3 . The percentage of water was calculated by difference in the case of ammonium salts and by heating the compound to a constant weight at 120° in the rest.

Conductometric Titrations.—0.1M solutions of ammonium phosphotellurate and the titrants BaCl_2 and CuSO_4 were prepared in conductivity water. Solutions of lower concentrations were obtained by appropriate dilution.

Definite volumes of ammonium salt solution were taken in a Pyrex beaker placed on a magnetic stirrer; cell was dipped properly and the initial conductance recorded by a Mullard conductivity bridge, type E 7566, direct reading electronic instrument. The titrants were added in small amounts from a microburette, the mixture stirred well, and the readings recorded after allowing the precipitate to settle. The end point was obtained graphically by plotting volume of the titrant added against the conductance. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Ammonium phosphotellurate soln. = 60 ml. Temp. = $25^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$.

Molarity of ammonium salt soln.	Molarity of the titrant.	Titre value.	Molar ratio of Am. salt: titrant.
	Copper sulphate.		
7.836×10^{-5}	9.979×10^{-2}	0.140 ml	1 : 2.98
1.959×10^{-4}	9.979×10^{-2}	0.350	1 : 2.98
2.743×10^{-4}	9.979×10^{-2}	0.495	1 : 3.01
	Barium chloride.		
1.959×10^{-4}	10.04×10^{-2}	0.350	1 : 2.99
3.917×10^{-4}	10.04×10^{-2}	0.700	1 : 2.98
5.876×10^{-4}	10.04×10^{-2}	1.040	1 : 2.96

DISCUSSION

Telluric acid is found to condense with phosphoric acid, as observed by Weinland and Prause¹. Its condensation reactions with molybdic acid are well known. Thus it became possible that telluric acid could be condensed with phosphoric and molybdic acid to form hetero-tri-salt. The composition of these salts has been arrived at on the basis of analytical results, as it is difficult to assign definite structures owing to the large size of the molecules. In conductometric titration the break at the molar ratio of ammonium-phosphotellurate to BaCl_2 and CuSO_4 solutions at 1:3 lend support to the formation of the respective salts reported. Conductometric titration was not possible in the case of cuprammonium salt because it liberated ammonia in aqueous solution on keeping for sometime.

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